

musée suisse du jeu
schweizer spielmuseum
swiss museum of games

Play and Games in Antiquity

Definition, Transmission, Reception

Swiss Museum of Games
September 17-19, 2018

Wall painting (H. 36 cm, L. 70 cm), Pompéi (IX, 3, 5), 69-79 CE. Naples, Museo Archeologico Nazionale, inv. 9103

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OUR HERITAGE:
WHERE THE PAST
MEETS THE FUTURE

Monday 17th September

10:15 OPENING - Véronique Dasen, Michel Fuchs, Ulrich Schädler
In Search of Ancient Games and Play

DEFINITION

10:30 Mark Golden, Winnipeg
Play, Dance, Sport, War: Ancient Greek Bodies in Motion

11:15 Stephen Kidd, Brown University (by skype)
Is play an Emotion? An Inquiry into Greek Paidia

11:45 Christian Laes, Antwerp
Ludus and Education

12:30 Miguel Herrero de Jáuregui, Madrid
Early Christian Attitudes to Child Playing

13:15 Brunch

14:15 Anton Bierl, Basel
Choral Dance as a Play: paizein in Greek Drama

15:00 Karin Schlapbach, Fribourg
Ludus as Dance and Bodily Movement

15:45 Break

BEGINNINGS AND ENDS

16:15 Marco Vespa, Fribourg
L'origine du jeu: récits grecs sur l'invention des pratiques ludiques entre Palamède, Prométhée et Theuth

17:00 Julien du Bouchet, Montpellier
Jouer en rêve : autour d'Artémidore

17:45 Break

18:15 Francesca Berti, Tübingen
Meanings of tradition in the Context of Play

EVENING LECTURE

19h15 Katarzyna Marciniak, Warsaw (ERC Our Mythical Childhood)
Du Rubicon à la chambre d'enfants ou à la réception de l'expression Alea iacta est dans la culture des jeunes / From Rubicon to the Children's Room, or the Reception of the Alea iacta est Motif in Youth Culture

Tuesday 18th September

MATERIAL DEFINITION

09:00 Regine Fellmann, Kantonsarchäologie Aargau, Brugg

Games and Toys From Vindonissa – An Overview

Barbara Pfäffli, Augusta Raurica

Augusta Raurica – Games of a Town

10:00 Break

10:15 Chiara Bianchi, Milano

“Alexandrian Counters” : Finds in Archaeological Contexts

11:00 Clare Rowan, Warwick (ERC Token Communities in the Ancient Mediterranean)

Sorting Fun From Fiction: Were “tesserae” Gaming Pieces?

11:45 Charles Doyen, Louvain

Osselets ou poids ?

12:30 Brunch

ICONOGRAPHIC DEFINITION

13:30 Vicky Sabetai, Athènes

Playing at the Festival: aiora, a Swinging Ritual

14:15 Michel Fuchs, Lausanne

Jeux d’Eros et jeux d’enfants : la corde, le dé et l’osselet en messagers du temps

15:00 Break

15:15 Nikolina Kei, Paris

Dessins et jeux fictifs

16:00 Arnaud Zucker, Nice

Les proverbes relatifs aux jeux chez Pollux et les parémiographes

16:45 Visit of the Swiss Museum of Games

18:00 Event Festival Images : Official opening of the artwork by Saype in the context of the Festival Images Vevey

EVENING LECTURE

19:15 Michel Manson, Toulouse

Un érudit inattendu : Louis Becq de Fouquières, le premier historien des jeux et jouets de l’Antiquité

Discutant : Louis-Aimé de Fouquière

Wednesday 19th September

RECEPTION

09:00 Simone Beta, Siena

Studiare la lingua e la letteratura greca divertendosi: gli indovinelli greci nelle scuole di Bisanzio/ Etudier la langue et la littérature en s'amusant: les devinettes grecques dans les écoles de Byzance

09:45 Renzo Tosi, Bologna

Pollux et les noms des jeux

10:30 Andromache Karanika, Irvine

Midas and the "Pot" Game: Intertextual Insights into an Ancient Game

11:15 Break

11:30 Salvatore Costanza, Fribourg

Pollux témoin des jeux : continuité, survie et réception dans la culture ludique néogrecque

12:15 Barbara Carè, Athens

Appropriating the Past: New Perspectives on Game Studies. The Ancient and Modern Game of Astragals

13:00 Lunch

Final discussion - conclusions

Play and Games in Antiquity

Definition, Transmission, Reception

Play and games provide a privileged access to past societal norms, values, identities, and collective imaginary. People play all over the world and throughout history, but they do not play the same games, nor do they attribute the same meaning and function to play. The aim of this pluridisciplinary conference is to investigate how this past patrimony can be methodologically reconstructed.

Three sessions will address first how the Ancients defined play and games by analysing their vocabulary in order to reconstruct an emic definition. Beyond the common association of child and play (in Greek, *paidia*, ‘game’, *pais*, the child, and *paideia*, ‘education’, share the same root, in Latin *ludus* means ‘play’, ‘school’ and ‘rethorical games’), the views are more complex and nuanced. Identifying ludic material and practices archaeologically as well as in iconography is also a debatable issue. The second session concerns the sources available and their bias associated with literary genre, such as oniromancy, proverbs and the lexicon of Pollux. A major challenge is the reconstruction of a mostly oral patrimony, of lost children’s lore and agency. The third session examines the transmission process of these practices from one generation to the next, addressing crucial issues about continuities and discontinuities, as well as about the definition of a “traditional” game.

Place

Musée Suisse du Jeu
Rue du Château 11
1814 La Tour-de-Peilz

Contacts & Organisation

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How to arrive

By train direction Villeneuve (S2 or S3)

Stop “Tour-de-Peilz”, then walk for 5 minutes.

By train + by bus

Train IR 90 direction Brig, stop “Vevey”, then take the bus 201 (direction Villeneuve) for 5 minutes until stop “La Tour-de-Peilz centre” or walk for 15 minutes.

